

EVOLYUSION JARAYONDA YASHASH UCHUN KURASH

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Annotasiya: Maqolada Ch.Darvin ta'limiga ko'ra evolyusion jarayonlar va yashash uchun kurash masalasi tabiatda qanday ask etishi haqida ma'lumotlar keltiriladi. O'simlik navlarini, xonaki xayvonlarni o'rganish asosida olingan xulosalarga tayanib xulosalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Nav, xayvonot, o'simlik, rang, nam, ko'payish.

Аннотация: В статье представлены сведения об эволюционных процессах и о том, как в природе решается вопрос борьбы за существование согласно учению Ч.Дарвина. Выводы сделаны на основе выводов, полученных на основе изучения сортов растений и домашних животных.

Ключевые слова: Сорт, животное, растение, окраска, влажность, размножение.

Abstract: The article presents information about how evolutionary processes and the struggle for existence, according to the teachings of Charles Darwin, arise in nature. The conclusions are drawn based on the study of plant varieties and domestic animals.

Keywords: Variety, animal, plant, color, moisture, reproduction.

Ch.Darvin madaniy o'simlik navlari, xonaki xayvon zotlarining xilma-xilligi, kelib chikish sababalarini aniklagandan keyin, tabiatdagi organizmlarning turli-tumanligini o'rganishgan uning sabablarini aniqlashga o'z e'tiborini karatdi.

Ch.Darvinni tabiiy sharoitda yashovchi xar bir o'simlik va xayvon ko'payganda o'zidan nixoyatda ko'p nasl qoldirishi xayron qoldirdi.

Ch.Darvin «Yashash uchun kurash» iborasini keng ma'noda, ya'ni organizmning o'zaro xamda anorganik tabiatning nokulay sharoitlari orasidagi murakkab va xilma-xil munosabatlarini, shuningdek, uzidan keyin normal nasl qoldirishini tushingan. Ch.Darvin kup yillik kuzatishlaridan sung yashash uchun kurashning uch xilini a) Tur ichidagi kurash b) Turlar orasidagi kurash v) Organizmlarning tabiatning noqulay sharoitlariga karshi kurashni farq qilgan.

a) Tur ichidagi kurash juda keskin buladi. Chunki, ularning oziqaga, yashash sharoitiga talabi, xavf-xatari bir xil buladi. Masalan, bir turga mansub yirtkichlar urtasida ulja talashish va ulja tutish bir xil buladi. Tur ichidagi kurash usimliklr dunyosida xam kuplab kuzatilgan. Masalan: shoxshabbasi keng kuloch yozgan baland daraxtlar kuyosh nuridan kuprok baxramand buladi. Baquvvat ildiz sistemasi yerdagi suv va unda erigan mineral moddalardan kuprok oziklanib, yon atrofidagi yosh daraxtlarni sikib kuyadi.

Baquvvat daraxtlar boshka daraxtlarni usishi va rivomslanishini tuxtatib, ularni butunlay nobud kiladi.

b) Turlar orasidagi yashash uchun kurash turli shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi. Masalan, Markaziy Osiyoda keyingi 30 yil mobaynida Xindiston maynasini kupayishi boshka kushlarning yashash uchun kurashda asta-sekin ular sonining kamayishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Shuningdek, yirtkich xayvon bilan uning uljasi, utxur xayvonlar bilan usimliklar, xashorotxur kush l ar bilan xashorotlar urtasidagi o'zaro munosabat, madaniy o'simliklar bilan begona urug'lar orasidagi raqobat, parazitlik qilib yashaydigan jigar qurti, cho'chka solityori, guzani urgimchak kanasi, karam kapalagini lichinkasi va madaniy o'simliklar xisobiga yashaydigan zarpechaklarni misol qilib olishimiz mumkin.

v) Organizmlarning tabiatni nokulay iklim sharoitiga qarshi kurashini xamma joyda kurishimiz mumkin. Odatda nami kam joylardagi o'simliklar qiska muddat

ichida, ya'ni baxorda gullab urug beradi. Boshqa o'simlik turlarini, chunonchi yantokning barglari mayda, ildizlari uzun buladi. Xavo xaroratining pasayishi bilan kushlar va sut emizuvchilarning pat va yunglari qalinlashadi, suvda xam quruklikda yashovchilar, sudralib yuruvchilar, umurtkasiz xayvonlar kishki uykuga ketadi. Bularning xammasi organizmlarning tabiatning noqulay sharoitiga qarshi kurashiga misol bo'ladi.

Tabiiy tanlanish xaqidagi tushuncha evolyusion ta'limot uchun muxim axamiyat ega. Ch.Darvin tabiiy -tanlanish deganda, foydali individual uzgarishlarga ega organizmlarning yashab kolishini, zararli uzgarishlarga ega organizmlarning kirilib ketishini, ya'ni moslashgan formalarning yashab qolishini, moslashmagan formalarning nobud bo'lishini nazarda tutgan.

Tabiiy tanlanish jarayonida organizmlar yashab kolishi yoki nobud oo'lishidan tashqari, ularning differensial urchishi xam muxim rol' o'ynaydi. Xozirgi zamon biologiyasida tabiiy tanlanishning uch xil shakli farqlanadi. a) Stabillashtiruvchn b) Xarakatlaitiruvchi v) Dpzruptiv.

a) Stabillashtiruvchi tanlanish. deb urtacha kiymatga ega bulgan mavjud belgi yoki xususiyatning populyasiyada saklanib kolishi va yuzaga chiqish imkoniyatlarini kuchaytirishga karatilgan tanlashga aytiladi. Agarda muxit sharoiti muayyan davr mobaynida nisbatan doimiy bulib kolsa, u xolda tabiiy tanlash uzgarmay, muayyan fenotipning adaptiv (eng kulay) «normasi» shakllanadi. Stabillovchi tanlashni bir kancha misollar bilan tushuntirish mumkin: Shimoliy Amerikada kuchli buron bilan kor yokkandan keyin ulim xolatidagi 136 ta chumchuk topilgan, ulardan 72 tasi tirik kolgan, 64 tasi o'lgan. Ulgan chumchuqlarning qanoti juda uzun yoki kisha ekanligi diqqatni o'ziga tortadi.

b) Xarakatlantiruvchi tanlanish deb ijobiy yunalishdagi, ya'ni o'rtacha qiymatli belgilarni kuchaytiruvchi yoki susaytiruvchi tanlashga aytiladi.

Muxit sharoiti uzgarishi bilan organizmning fenotipik xususiyatlari xam uzgara boshlaydi va bu ilgari vujudga kelgan genotip asosida yangi modifikasiya

paydo bulishiga olib keladi. Bunday modifikasiya yangi irsiy forma yaratmaydi, ammo u evolyusion tarakkiyot yunalishini kursatib turuvchi indikator vazifasini utaydi va shu tufayli muxim utish boskichi axamiyatga ega bo'ladi. Yangi fenotip ta'sirida genotip kayta kurila boshlaydi va bu yangilanish genotipik imkoniyatlar asosida ruyobga chikadigan fenotipga ega bola'di. Biror belgining (a'zoning) evolyusiya jarayonida yuqotilishi xarakterlan- tiruvchi tanlanish natijasidadir. Uz funksional axamiyatini yuqotgan a'zo tabiiy tanlanish natijasida reduksiyaga uchraydi. Ayrim qushlar va xashoratlarning kanotsiz bulishi, korongi joyda gorlarda yashovchi xayvonlarda ko'z bo'lmasligi, parazit o'simliklarda ildiz, barg b'lmasligi

xarakterlanuvchi tanlanish natijasidadir.

v) Dizruptiv tanlanish bir xil yashash imkoniyatiga ega bulgan turli xil fenotipik organizmlarni saklab koladi. Masalan, och jigari rang tuproqli o'rmonlarda tok shilliqurtining jigari rang yoki pushti rang chiganoqqa ega bo'lishi, dagal va sariq rangli utlar usgan joyda esa chiganogi sariq rangli xillari uchraydi. Chig'anoqni yashash muxitiga xos turli rangda bo'lishi kushlar (shillikkurtlarni) ko'plab kirishidan saqlaydi. Tok shillikkurtini jigari rang tuproqli o'rmonlarda jigari rang yoki pushti rang, dagal va sariq rangli o'tlar o'sgan joyda esa chiganogi sariq rangli bo'lishi tabiatda ximoya rangi ekanligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Bunga qushimcha qilib qishloq xo'jalik o'simliklariga zarar keltiradigan xashorot va zararkunandalar masalan (shiralarni o'simli maysaligida yashil rangga, pishish davrida jigari rangga uzgarishini) misol kilib olishimiz mumkin.

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